

Estimating the accuracy of the chromaticity calibration from BP/RP data

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Abstract

The chromaticity in the astrometric field of Gaia must be calibrated to high accuracy using photometric information from the BP and RP spectra. This note outlines a procedure for the chromaticity calibration which allows to estimate the residual errors after calibration, both due to modelling errors and the noisy BP/RP data.

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1 Introduction

One of the scientific requirements for Gaia (SCI-340) is that the photometers should provide sufficient information about the spectral energy distribution (SED) of each object at each transit to allow a sufficiently good calibration (and hence correction) of the chromatic image shifts in the astrometric field.¹ In the DPAC data processing the chromaticity correction is essentially a part of the LSF calibration; i.e., the LSF is calibrated as function of the SED as well as of the position in the field, time, etc. If the LSF calibration is done correctly, no remaining chromaticity will be seen in the astrometric solution.

Because the LSF calibration is very complex, the DPAC approach to handling the chromaticity is not suitable for demonstrating that requirement SCI-340 can be met. A different approach was taken in some earlier studies [see Lindegren (GAIA-LL-039) and Lindegren (GAIA-LL-049)], namely to model the centroid shift (suitably defined) as function of the relative fluxes in the BBP photometric bands. It is proposed that a similar procedure can be used with the BP/RP spectra in order to demonstrate the feasibility of the calibration. This procedure is outlined in Sect. 2, and further details are given in subsequent sections. It relies heavily on concepts developed rather recently within DPAC, especially in Lindegren (LL-080), to which reference is frequently made in the following.

It should be noted that the requirement actually consists of two parts: first, that adequate *calibration* of the chromaticity effect is possible (e.g., using bright stars and a very large number of observations); and secondly that *correction* is possible (e.g., even in the case of the noisy BP/RP data from a single transit of a faint star). The proposed procedure covers both parts.

2 Summary of the procedure

It is assumed that for every astrometric transit there are also registrations of the BP and RP spectra. In order for them to provide sufficient information for the chromaticity calibration, they have to be photometrically calibrated, i.e., put on correct wavelength scales and corrected for variations of the spectral response. However, since the photometric calibration may be decoupled from the chromaticity calibration, it will be assumed that the BP and RP spectra used as input below have been properly calibrated.

A large library of astrophysical SEDs (spectral energy distributions) is needed for the procedure. The SED gives the incident monochromatic flux (e.g., in photons $\text{s}^{-1} \text{m}^{-2} \text{nm}^{-1}$) as

¹SCI-340 reads (ESA Gaia Project, GAIA-EST-RD-00553): “The number of photometric bands in SCI-330 shall provide the spectral energy distribution of each object at each epoch of observation with an accuracy sufficient for calibrating chromatic effects with end-of-mission residuals of less than $2.5 \mu\text{as}$ for objects with $V = 15$ and $30 \mu\text{as}$ for objects with $V = 20$. The calibration of chromatic effects shall be performed at the same epoch and angular resolution as the astrometric measurements.”

function of wavelength for an object of specified magnitude, e.g., $V = 0$. Two such sets must be provided:

- The calibration set: these SEDs cover a wide range of normal stellar types including various degrees of interstellar extinction. These stellar types will be encountered in large numbers during the mission, and can therefore reasonably be used for calibration purposes.
- The validation set: these SEDs include both normal stellar types (not included in the calibration set) and some objects with more peculiar spectra, such as emission-line stars and quasars at different redshifts. The calibration model must work well enough also for these objects, even though they are not numerous enough to be used for the calibration itself.

The idea is to use the calibration set to make the chromaticity calibration, and the validation set to evaluate the predictive power of that calibration. Both sets can be used to evaluate how photometric errors in the BP and RP data propagate into the chromaticity estimate.

The procedure can then be summarized in the following steps:

1. For each SED in the calibration and validation sets, calculate the polychromatic LSF $L(u|\text{SED})$ in the astrometric field (AF) for a number of representative WFE maps (e.g., one per AF CCD). The origin of the LSF (where $u = 0$) must represent a physically well-defined point in the optical field of view, which is independent of the SED; for example, it could be the geometrical position of the chief ray, or it could be chosen so that the WFE has no tip/tilt component. Then compute for each LSF the location of the centroid (u_0), using Tukey's biweight with $s = 2.7$ pixels (Lindgren, LL-068).
2. For each SED in the calibration and validation sets, calculate the effective spectral shape coefficients s_i defined in Sect. 3.
3. Using the calibration set only, make a linear regression of u_0 versus s_i (without constant term), i.e., a linear least-squares solution of the condition equations

$$\sum_{i=0}^{N-1} C_i s_i \simeq u_0 \quad (1)$$

A separate regression is made for each WFE map (CCD). The regression coefficients C_i constitute the chromaticity calibration for that CCD. The RMS residual of the regression is a first indication of how well the chromaticity can be calibrated by means of BP/RP data within the given model (1).

4. Using the validation set, calculate the RMS prediction error for each SED/WFE combination. This is a better indication of the actual accuracy of the calibration than the RMS residual from the calibration set. i.e., the size of the systematic component of the chromaticity residuals.

The above steps address the first part of the requirement, namely whether a calibration is possible (with the adopted linear model) in the limiting case of noiseless spectral information. This is a reasonable approximation since the chromaticity calibration will in practice be made using bright stars, for which the noise in the BP and RP data is quite small, and can be based on a very large number of observations.

To address the second part of the requirement, the noise in the BP/RP data for a single transit must be propagated through the calibration model to give the size of the random component of the chromaticity residuals. Using the calibration values C_i established in Step 3, the following steps are needed:

5. For each SED in the calibration set, simulate the BP/RP samples for a single transit of a star of the assumed magnitude, including Poisson, readout, and other relevant noises.
6. Use the simulated samples to calculate the *estimated* effective spectral shape coefficients \hat{s}_i as described in Sect. 4. These estimated values differ slightly from the theoretical ('true') ones, s_i from Step 2, due to the noise in the BP/RP data.
7. Calculate the corresponding error in the chromaticity correction. For the linear model in Eq. (1) it is given by

$$\Delta u_0 = \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} C_i \times (\hat{s}_i - s_i) \quad (2)$$

8. Collect statistics of Δu_0 as function of magnitude.

Several different noise realizations, as well as different sub-pixel spectrum locations (κ and κ' in Eq. 6), will be needed for each SED/magnitude combination.

3 Definition of the effective spectral shape coefficients

In Lindegren (LL-080) is described how an arbitrary SED, represented by the function $F^\lambda(\lambda)$ (in photons per wavelength unit, as function of wavelength) can be approximated by a linear

combination of *spectral basis functions* $B_i^\lambda(\lambda)$,

$$F^\lambda(\lambda) \simeq \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} f_i B_i^\lambda(\lambda) \quad (3)$$

where f_i are referred to as the *spectral coefficients*. A specific example for the choice of basis functions, applicable to the Gaia AF/BP/RP instruments, is given in Eqs. (20)–(21) of Lindegren (LL-080). It uses $N = 11$ basis functions, thus defining 11 spectral coefficients for each SED. This particular choice of spectral basis functions may be adopted for the present purpose.

The chromaticity is independent of the flux level, so the interesting quantities are not the spectral coefficients f_i themselves, but normalized values (whose sum equals 1) that only describe the shape of the SED. Such coefficients may be called *spectral shape coefficients*.

However, it is also obvious that the chromaticity cannot depend on the part of the spectrum for which the spectral response of the AF instrument is zero. More generally, it can be assumed that chromaticity only depends on the effective SED, $F^\lambda(\lambda)R^{\text{AF}}(\lambda)$, where $R^{\text{AF}}(\lambda)$ is the response function of the AF instrument, i.e., the product of the transmittance and quantum efficiency.

Following Eqs. (10)–(11) in Lindegren (LL-080) we therefore define the *effective spectral coefficients* in AF as $f_i r_i^{\text{AF}}$, where

$$r_i^{\text{AF}} = \int_0^\infty B_i^\lambda(\lambda) R^{\text{AF}}(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (4)$$

and subsequently the *effective spectral shape coefficients* as

$$s_i = \frac{f_i r_i^{\text{AF}}}{\sum_{j=0}^{N-1} f_j r_j^{\text{AF}}} \quad (5)$$

(Naturally, s_i is also specific for AF, but the superscript AF is here suppressed for simplicity.) The effective spectral shape coefficients are normalized to $\sum_i s_i = 1$, which is why the linear regression in Eq. (1) does not need a constant term.

The response function $R^{\text{AF}}(\lambda)$ will in reality be slightly different for the different CCDs (and also as function of other parameters). However, in order to have a single set of parameters s_i for each SED, a typical (reference) response function for AF should be used. This is in line with the previous assumption that the instrument is already photometrically calibrated.

To summarize the various spectral parameters introduced in this section:

- The spectral coefficients (f_i) represent the SED, $F^\lambda(\lambda)$: they are specific for the object.
- The effective spectral coefficients ($f_i r_i$) represent the effective SED, $F^\lambda(\lambda)R(\lambda)$: they are specific for the object/instrument combination.

- The spectral shape coefficients represent the shape of the SED: they are specific for the object but independent of its magnitude.
- The effective spectral shape coefficients (s_i) represent the shape of the effective SED: they are specific for the object/instrument combination but independent of magnitude.

4 Estimating effective spectral shape coefficients from BP/RP data

After bias and gain correction, and subtraction of the background level, the result of an individual BP+RP crossing is a set of sample values N_k^{BP} , $N_{k'}^{\text{RP}}$ (in electrons). Following Lindegren (LL-080) they can be modelled as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} N_k^{\text{BP}} &= \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} f_i \times r_i^{\text{BP}} L_i^{\text{BP}}(k - \kappa) + \text{noise} \\ N_{k'}^{\text{RP}} &= \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} f_i \times r_i^{\text{RP}} L_i^{\text{RP}}(k' - \kappa') + \text{noise} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

where f_i are the previously defined spectral coefficients,

$$r_i^{\text{XP}} = \int_0^\infty B_i^\lambda(\lambda) R^{\text{XP}}(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (7)$$

are the response coefficients of the XP instrument (XP = BP or RP), and

$$L_i^{\text{XP}}(u) = (r_i^{\text{XP}})^{-1} \int_0^\infty L_\lambda^{\text{XP}} [u - D^{\text{XP}}(\lambda)] B_i^\lambda(\lambda) R^{\text{XP}}(\lambda) d\lambda \quad (8)$$

are the quasi-monochromatic LSFs in XP corresponding to the spectral basis functions $B_i^\lambda(\lambda)$. As shown by Eqs. (7)–(8), the quasi-monochromatic LSFs are essentially weighted averages of the appropriately shifted monochromatic LSFs $L_\lambda^{\text{XP}}(u)$, where the shift is given by the dispersion function $D^{\text{XP}}(\lambda)$ and the relative weights by the product of the spectral basis function and the photometric response function $R^{\text{XP}}(\lambda)$ of the relevant instrument (XP).

It can be assumed that κ and κ' , the locations of the BP and RP spectra in the pixel streams, are known from the astrometric position of the object combined with the wavelength calibrations of the photometric instruments. Moreover, the coefficients r_i^{XP} are also assumed to be known. Equation (6) therefore constitutes a linear model for the estimation of the spectral coefficients f_i . They can for example be determined by a weighted least-squares fit to the whole set of sample values N_k^{BP} , $N_{k'}^{\text{RP}}$ obtained in the BP/RP transit. Using proper statistical weighting (depending on the Poisson and readout noise of the sample values), this provides a nearly optimal determination of f_i from a single transit. Multiplying by the known r_i^{AF} and normalizing gives the effective spectral shape coefficients according to Eq. (5).

5 Possible problems with the calibration model

The simple linear model in Eq. (1) may be problematic in several different respects. Two potential problems, and their remedies, are briefly considered here.

Near-singularity. Depending on the number of coefficients, N , and the properties of the calibration set, it could be that the least-squares problem in Eq. (1) is singular or nearly singular. If it is singular, the usual solution method will of course fail. But even in the near-singular case, it is likely that the calibration coefficients will be numerically large and unstable, resulting in bad performance for the validation set. Two remedies are suggested: (i) reduce the number of parameters s_i , for example by combining neighbouring ones into a new coefficients (preserving the sum of s_i); or (ii) make a pseudo-solution, or a regularized solution, minimizing $\sum_i C_i^2$, for example using the SVD algorithm.

Model misfit. If the RMS residual of the fit is too large, a more accurate model is needed. Since in that case the linear model with $N \sim 11$ bands is inadequate, it is not likely that increasing N will help. One must then resort to more general, non-linear models. For example, the quadratic regression discussed in Lindegren (GAIA-LL-039) (Eq. 7) can be tried.

6 Summary

A procedure is outlined for estimating both the systematic and random errors of the chromaticity calibration. The systematic errors depend on how well the model represents the centroid shifts for different spectral energy distributions (SEDs). The random errors come from the propagation of Poisson and readout noise in the BP/RP samples via the calibration model into the chromaticity corrections for a single transit of the object across the AF.

Although the procedure is very different from how chromaticity will be handled by DPAC, its successful application will be enough to demonstrate that also the DPAC approach should work.

In order to apply the proposed procedure, DPAC should provide a large database of representative SEDs, specifying what should be included in the calibration set and in the validation set.

Furthermore, it will be necessary to clarify exactly how the numerical results of the procedure (RMS calibration residuals, and RMS Δu_0 , from the calibration and validation sets) shall be interpreted in relation to the requirements in SCI-340.

7 References

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